

Anjania, Badidhan, Badshahbhog, Bangoli 3, Budiabanko, Bansbhira, Barhi, Barik safed, Basangi, Lal Basant, Bataru, Benwar, Bewara, Banspatri, Bhakawa, and Chapdo were resistant; Bakalu, Bagri, Basant dhoura, Benisar halka, Bewra hara, Bhaji, Badi, and Chhatri were moderately resistant. These cultivars are popular for direct sowing under rainfed conditions. They are drought tolerant and mature within 120 d. □

Mode of feeding on selected wild rices and weight gain of first-instar larvae of rice leaffolder (LF)

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We measured the leaf area consumed and weight gain by two rice LF species—*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) and *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley—feeding on wild rice leaves in the laboratory. The wild rices were *Oryza officinalis*, *O. perennis*, *O. punctata*, *O. nivara*, and *O. australiensis*. IR36 and TKM6 were the susceptible and resistant checks.

Filter paper discs 2.5 cm in diam were placed on the bottoms of 30-ml plastic cups and moistened with distilled water to maintain humidity and leaf turgor. A 2-cm-long leaf-cut from the middle portion of leaves of 30-d-old plants and 10 1d-old, first-instar larvae from insectary culture at IRRI were placed in each cup and the cups were closed with a tight-fitting paper lid. Cups were arranged in a randomized complete block design in an incubator at 26-28°C and 40% relative humidity for 48 h.

Leaf area consumed was measured using an automatic area meter (Model AAM-7, Hayashi Denkoh Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). Percent increase in larva body weight was measured by recording individual larval weight before and after 48 h feeding.

Leaf area consumed differed significantly. *C. medinalis* larvae consumed a significantly bigger leaf area

Leaf area consumed and percent weight gain by 1-d-old, first-instar LF larvae after 48 h on selected wild rices.^a IRRI, 1988.

Treatment	LF species		Difference ^b
	<i>C. medinalis</i>	<i>M. patnalis</i>	
	<i>Leaf area consumed^c (cm²)</i>		
<i>O. officinalis</i>	0.923 ± 0.211 ab	0.518 ± 0.041 b	0.405**
<i>O. perennis</i>	0.903 ± 0.350 abc	0.408 ± 0.137 bc	0.515**
<i>O. punctata</i>	0.699 ± 0.199 c	0.523 ± 0.046 b	0.176*
<i>O. nivara</i>	0.310 ± 0.107 d	0.342 ± 0.045 cd	-0.032ns
<i>O. australiensis</i>	0.734 ± 0.205 bc	0.233 ± 0.107 d	0.501**
IR36 (susceptible check)	1.104 ± 0.203 a	0.981 ± 0.158 a	0.123ns
TKM6 (resistant check)	0.681 ± 0.147 c	0.382 ± 0.144 c	0.299**
	<i>Percent weight gain^d</i>		
<i>O. officinalis</i>	178 ± 49.65 c	151 ± 37.06 a	27ns
<i>O. perennis</i>	155 ± 37.55 bc	198 ± 37.21 bc	-43**
<i>O. punctata</i>	134 ± 40.91 ab	177 ± 66.55 abc	-43ns
<i>O. nivara</i>	160 ± 52.34 bc	148 ± 56.19 a	12ns
<i>O. australiensis</i>	163 ± 49.91 bc	168 ± 34.16 ab	- 5ns
IR36 (susceptible check)	161 ± 61.01 bc	203 ± 49.34 c	-42ns
TKM6 (resistant check)	102 ± 45.89 a	166 ± 41.82 ab	-64**

^a For leaf area consumed and percent weight gain in a column, means (±SD) followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b ns = not significant, ** = significant at 1% level, * = significant at 5% level by t-test. ^c Ten larvae/replication; av of 9 replications. ^d One larva/replication; av of 14 replications.

of susceptible IR36, *O. officinalis*, and *O. perennis* than of resistant TKM6 and the three other wild rices (see table). *M. patnalis* larvae consumed significantly less leaf area of all the wild rices and resistant TKM6 than of IR36. *C. medinalis* larvae consumed significantly more on all the wild rices except *O. nivara* than did *M. patnalis* larvae.

Larvae of both species gained weight on all host plants tested. Weight gained

by *C. medinalis* larvae on wild rices was comparable to that gained by those feeding on susceptible IR36. *M. patnalis* gained less weight on *O. officinalis*, *O. nivara*, *O. australiensis*, and TKM6 than on susceptible IR36. Although *C. medinalis* larvae consumed more than did *M. patnalis* larvae, percent weight gain increase in *M. patnalis* was higher than in *C. medinalis* on resistant TKM6 and *O. perennis* wild rice. □

Comparison of steam and molecular distillation methods in rice

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In our search for the chemical basis of rice resistance to insect pests, we are developing a method to extract volatiles from rice plants so that the extract resembles the volatiles the plant emits naturally to the environment, in enough quantity to evaluate their biological activity.

With the steam distillation used traditionally, there has always been a question of extract quality because of

the drastic conditions of the method.

We evaluated qualitative differences in volatile composition of molecular and steam distillates from IR26 using gas chromatography (GC).

Fresh foliage from 45-d-old plants was cut in 5-cm pieces and 100 g placed in a 500-ml glass container connected to one end of a 10-cm-long U tube. On the other end, the distillate was collected in a glass thimble. A high vacuum valve was connected 5 cm over the thimble.

The sample container was immersed in a Dewar flask containing dry ice/acetone for 20 min. The system was connected to a high vacuum line and the air evacuated until the inside pressure reached 10⁻³ mm Hg. The high vacuum valve was closed, the Dewar flask was